

The Working Mechanism of the Brain in Maintaining Physical, Psychological, And Spiritual Balance Through Emotional Management: Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: This study is a systematic literature review that aims to explore the working mechanisms of the brain in maintaining physical, psychological, and spiritual balance through emotional management. Using the PRISMA approach, this study interpreted 108 relevant journals, then conducted an in-depth review of 16 selected literatures from national and international sources (2015–2025). The results of this review include the working mechanisms of the brain in regulating cognitive, emotional, and behavioral functions, as well as physiological responses that activated by the HPA axis through emotional management. In addition, the Islamic spiritual approach—with the implementation of prayer practices, dhikr, and reading the Qur'an—is described as an effective stress management strategy through reducing physiological stress and improving mental well-being. The research findings indicate that the integration of biology, psychology, and spiritual values can provide a holistic approach in dealing with emotional disorders and stress, and open up opportunities for more comprehensive interventions to restore the balance of body and soul. The implications of this study serve as a basis for developing intervention therapies that combine scientific and spiritual aspects to improve the quality of mental health amidst the pressures of modern life.

KEYWORDS: Emotion, Physiological Psychology, Spiritual

INTRODUCTION

Emotions and stress are two basic components that are important in human life. Both affect the human thinking process, feeling, and behavior. Discussion of emotions and stress has become crucial lately. Many scientific studies have examined both of these things in more depth. Emotions involve the nervous system and hormones from a biological perspective, as well as a person's psychological reactions in the form of expressions and so on. While stress, an unbalanced condition that results in a person's mental health that can disrupt the body's physiological balance through physiological psychological mechanisms such as activation of the HPA axis (hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal).

The balance between physical, psychological, and spiritual aspects is the main foundation in maintaining a person's mental and emotional stability. From a physiological psychology perspective, the relationship between biological and psychological systems shows that humans play a role in forming emotional reactions, including in dealing with stress. When someone experiences psychological stress, the body responds through the work of the nervous system and hormones which have a direct impact on emotional conditions and overall well-being.

Meanwhile, in religious teachings, emotions and stress also receive great attention. Religion provides comprehensive guidance through spiritual values such as patience, sincerity, gratitude, and worship such as prayer and dhikr. All of these are believed to be able to help calm the mind and deal with the pressures of life better. Stress in the context of religious teachings is not only seen as a psychological problem caused by emotional disturbances and stress where both are interconnected, but stress is also seen as a test of faith that can be a means to get closer to God.

However, discussions that integrate emotions, stress, and spirituality are still few. Likewise, studies that integrate religious views with physiological psychology in understanding the relationship between emotions, stress, and the balance of the body and soul. Therefore, this review aims to examine relevant academic literature to explore the working mechanisms of the brain in the complex relationship between biological, psychological, and spiritual aspects through emotional management.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used is *systematic literature review* (SLR) using the PRISMA technique. This aims to interpret the literature that has been collected as many as 108 random journals, regarding the discussion of emotions and stress, as well as the correlation of physiology in spiritual aspects. The journals used are of national and international standards. The sources of literature are *Media Neliti*, *PoP*, *Google Scholar*, and *Reasearchgate* . The year of publication of the journals used is 2015 to 2025. A total of 16 literatures were *reviewed* using descriptive qualitative methodology and used as research materials.

Chart 1. Steps to Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

In chart 1, the *Systematic Literature Review (SLR) Steps* are carried out in 4 stages: Identification, *Screening*, Eligibility, and Final Inclusion. In the initial stage, researchers collect references from various sources such as *Media Neliti*, *PoP*, *Google Scholar*, and *Reasearchgate* . Furthermore, an initial *screening* or filtering process is carried out on the articles that have been collected. 51 articles that passed *the screening* were then analyzed to ensure the inclusion criteria. In the final stage, 16 articles were obtained that were considered feasible and relevant which would be the material for in-depth analysis. These articles are the main foundation for explaining the relationship between biological-psychological mechanisms and spiritual interventions, especially in the context of stress management and emotional balance in the perspective of physiological psychology and Islam.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

After obtaining a number of literatures that are in accordance with the research topic, the researcher attaches the results of the data analysis according to the journal article title, journal name, volume and page, year of authorship, and research results.

Table 1: Research Results

No.	Title	Journal Name	Vol. and Page.	Year	Writer	Research result
1.	The Relationship Between Resilience and Stress in Civil Service College Students	Journal of Psychology Research	Vol. 07, Page 65	2016	Tria Septiani, Nurindah Fitriani	Stress is an unpleasant experience experienced by students due to various causal factors in the form of <i>stressors</i> , namely frustration, conflict, pressure, change, and reactions, namely physiological reactions, emotional reactions, behavioral reactions, and cognitive assessments of the stress experienced.
2.	Analysis of Daniel Goleman's Theory in the Development of Emotional Intelligence in Early Childhood	Absorbent Mind: Journal of Psychology and Child Development	Vol. 4, p. 160	2024	Risma Chintya, Masganti Sit	Emotions are feelings that fluctuate in every individual that can cause changes in facial expressions, feelings that will ultimately result in actions to express these emotions, such as crying, laughing, being moved, angry, and so on.
3.	The Relationship Between Stress and High Blood Pressure in College Students	Islamic Studies and Maqashid	Vol. 2, pp. 4 - 7	2015	Subramania m, V.	The results of this study indicate that stress in students that can cause high blood pressure is an internal condition, which can be caused by physical demands (body), or the environment, and social situations, which have the potential to be damaging and uncontrolled.
4.	Emotional Regulation and Psychological Well-being of	Journal of Islamic Psychology	Vol. 9, pp. 57 - 68	2022	Reskido, A., Sutra, S., Oksanda, E., Nashori F.	The results of this study show that emotional regulation is positively correlated with psychological well-being.

	Muslim Students					
5.	Emotions in Cross-Cultural Perspective	Innovative: Journal Of Social Science Research	Vol.2 No.1	2022	Lilik Anton Budiono, Musa Each	Subjective psychophysical and emotional reactions affect a person's mental health, body, and behavior. Various types of basic emotions - fear, anger, sadness, joy, surprise, disgust, and irritation - are manifested through various body and facial reactions that indicate a person's character.
6.	Overview of Academic Stress Levels in Final Year Students Who Are Writing Their Thesis	Journal of Education of Batang Hari	Vol 4 No 10	2022	Helmy Ramadhan, Oktariani	Stress is the body and mind's reaction to pressure or demands that are perceived to be greater than a person's capacity. Stress can affect a person's physical, emotional, cognitive, and behavioral health when there is a mismatch between environmental demands and a person's capacity to handle them.
7.	Self Disclosure and Stress Levels in Students Working on Their Thesis	Scientific journal of psychology	Vol 5 No 1	2018	Witrin Gamayanti, Mahardianis a, Isop Syafei	The results of this study indicate that self-disclosure does not have a significant effect on stress levels in students who are working on their thesis. Self-disclosure only explains 0.9% of the variation in stress levels, while the rest is influenced by other factors such as emotional regulation, self-efficacy, and self-esteem. Students tend to do self-disclosure superficially without a clear purpose, so it is not effective in reducing stress.
8.	Social Support: As an Aid to Deal with Stress Among	Journal of Education Sciences and Teacher	Vol 12 No 02	2023	Fatima the daughter of	The results of this study indicate that social support plays an important role in helping orphaned adolescents

	Adolescent Orphans in Orphanages	Training				cope with the stress of losing a parent. Support from family, friends, teachers, and caregivers provides a sense of being loved and appreciated, and improves psychological well-being. High social support can reduce mental stress, while low support increases the risk of psychological disorders and adjustment difficulties.
9.	Understanding Anxiety: An Islamic Psychology Perspective	Indonesian Journal of Islamic Psychology	Vol. 02 No. 01, Pages 14-15	2020	Aditya Dedy Nugraha	This study used a literature review method and found that Islamic psychotherapy is effective in reducing anxiety. Some of the techniques used include dhikr, reading Al-Fatihah reflectively, and listening to murottal and prayers. Dhikr therapy has been proven to calm the heart and reduce physical and psychological symptoms of anxiety, especially in pregnant women.
10.	Spiritual Dimensions in Psychotherapy: The Impact of Sufi Practices on Anxiety and Depression	DA'WA: Journal of Islamic Guidance, Counseling & Guidance	Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 14 - 24	2024	Imroatul Husna and Khodijah	Sufi practices, such as dhikr, muhasabah, and tawakal are effective in reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression in participants. Decreased heart rate, blood pressure, and sleep patterns were found as physiological effects of consistent dhikr. Muhasabah helps individuals process emotions more healthily, reduces mental stress, and increases self-awareness. Tawakal helps individuals accept, which has a direct impact on reducing depression. The results show that spirituality in Islam can be

						an effective psychological intervention method in managing stress and emotions.
11.	The Qur'an and Psychology: A Spiritual Approach to Mental Health	ULIL ALBAB: Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal	Vol. 4 No. 2, pp. 831- 850	2025	Goddess Taviana Walida	Patience, sincerity, tawakal, and dhikr, play a role in maintaining the balance of the soul in the Qur'an and have a positive impact on mental and physical health. This spiritual practice can reduce cortisol levels (stress hormones) which affect peace of mind.
12.	Integration of Psychology and Islamic Spirituality in a Holistic Approach to Trauma Recovery	Saneskara: Journal of Social Studies	Vol. 1No. 2 (2024)	2024	Syifa, S., & Nurjannah, N.	Holistic approach that integrates psychology, and Islamic spiritualism is effective in trauma recovery such as Patience, Ikhlas, Tawakal, Al-Quran and Dhikr. This model not only addresses the psychological aspect, but also fulfills the spiritual needs of the individual, making it more effective than conventional therapy.
13.	Stress Response Mechanisms: An Integrational Conceptualization of Islam and the West	Psych Journal of Islamic Psychology	Vol. 5 No. 1(2019)	2019	Martyrdom of Rena	Integration of Western psychology and Islamic spirituality in understanding and managing stress can provide a more comprehensive and effective approach. By combining psychological techniques and spiritual practices, individuals can better cope with and overcome stress in everyday life.
14.	Mental Disorders in the Perspective of Islamic Mental Health	An-Nida, Journal of Islamic Thought	Vol. 40 No. 01, pp. 23-27	2015	Drs. Suhaimi, M.Ag	Mental disorders in the perspective of Islamic mental health are understood as conditions that are not only influenced by biological, psychological, and socio-cultural factors, but also by

						spiritual imbalance. In modern society, the advancement of science has caused spiritual aridity that triggers various mental problems. Unfortunately, the negative stigma against people with mental disorders is still strong, especially due to the traditional belief that the disorder comes from supernatural powers such as jinn or magic.
15.	Depression and Anxiety in Adolescents Reviewed from Health and Islamic Perspectives	Jo-DEST: Journal of Demography, Ethnography, and Social Transformation	Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 35-44	2021	Hafifatul Auliya Rahmy, Muslimahayati	Stress or depression is a common thing when someone is faced with trials and then feelings of sadness and anxiety arise. However, each of these feelings needs to be controlled so that it is not excessive because excessive feelings will certainly cause illness. In Islam, the approach to religious therapy certainly refers to the Qur'an and the Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad SAW. Ibn Qayyim stated that the Qur'an is a cure for various diseases, both heart and physical diseases (Al-Baqarah: 2).
16.	Sugar Intake and Psychological Effects on the Human Body	AL MIKRAJ Journal of Islamic Studies and Humanities	Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 918-926	2024	Ivory Giovani Putri	Sweet foods and drinks are considered to be able to improve <i>mood</i> and ease emotional conditions, so that someone who is stressed tends to crave (snack) or is called " <i>comfort food</i> ". Studies show that individuals who are depressed tend to choose " <i>comfort food</i> " to ease their emotional condition. <i>China Health and Nutrition Survey</i> , found that respondents who

						<p>experience stress tend to choose <i>fast food</i> rather than consuming vegetables and fruits. Although sugar intake can relieve stress, if sugar consumption is too high in the long term, there will be dangerous risks such as diabetes mellitus and obesity.</p>
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DISCUSSION

A systematic review of 16 scientific literatures published between 2015 and 2025, stress and emotions are two important factors that have a significant impact on human mental and physical health. These findings highlight the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to understanding and managing stress and emotional reactions, especially when combining physiological psychology with Islamic spiritual principles (Budiono & Musa Masing, 2022).

According to the results of various studies, stress is characterized as a state of tension experienced by a person when they believe that the demands of their environment are greater than their ability to cope (Ramadhan, 2022). A number of stressors, including pressure, conflict, frustration, and change, can cause academic stress in students (Septiani & Fitria, 2016). Stress triggers various body reactions, including physiological reactions such as increased heart rate, emotions such as anxiety and anger, behaviors such as withdrawal or isolation, and cognitive such as difficulty concentrating. This is consistent with the activation of the HPA axis of the physiological psychological system, which controls the body's reaction to psychological stress by releasing the stress hormone cortisol (Muslimahayati & Rahmy, 2021). The HPA axis is the body's neuroendocrine system involving the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, and adrenal glands. This complex communication system is responsible for handling stress reactions by regulating cortisol production. The part of *the limbic system* involved in this HPA axis response is the hypothalamus. Part of the hypothalamus, namely the paraventricular nucleus (PVN), produces *corticotropin releasing factor* (CRF) which is released into the blood vessels and the pituitary porta hypothalamus. Furthermore, CRF affects the anterior pituitary gland to stimulate the release of adrenocorticotrop hormone (ACTH) into the bloodstream. When it reaches the adrenal cortex, ACTH will stimulate the release of adrenal cortex hormones. As long as there is stress, there will be an increase in HPA axis activity in the form of increased CRF, and ACTH which triggers cortisol production. However, if stress continues , HPA axis activity will decrease again as before stress (Yuliadi, 2021).

Figure 1 Illustration of the body's reaction to stress by releasing the stress hormone cortisol.

Source: <https://www.verywellhealth.com/cortisol>

Continuous stress can cause long-term health problems such as diabetes, high blood pressure, and a decreased immune system (Subramaniam, 2015).

A person's psychological state is also greatly influenced by emotions which are uncontrollable reactions. Emotions are feelings that arise naturally and affect a person's behavior and facial expressions (Chintya & Sit, 2024). Emotions can change and are greatly influenced by psychological conditions and environmental factors. Maintaining mental balance requires emotional control. Research has found that Muslim students show better psychological well-being when they are able to control their emotions (Reskido et al., 2022). However, not all techniques for managing emotions are successful in controlling stress. *Self-disclosure* without specific goals and directions does not have a real impact on reducing stress (Gamayanti et al., 2018).

Various ways can be done to manage stress. Research also shows that eating habits often function as a means of stress relief. Individuals who experience stress, emotionally often consume *comfort food* or sweet foods to relieve stress quickly (Mikraj & Putri, 2024).

Environmental and social support elements are also important for managing stress and emotions. According to research, orphaned adolescents who receive social and emotional support from their surroundings, such as from peers, caregivers, and orphanages tend to be more mentally resilient when dealing with emotional stress (Ibda, 2023). This support directly reduces psychological stress and encourages more constructive adaptation by offering a sense of security, acceptance, and affection. Active individual involvement in positive activities such as volunteering, community service, and organizations is also one way to avoid symptoms of stress due to overthinking, which can be caused by a lack of positive activities.

In addition, spiritual approaches have been shown to significantly reduce symptoms of anxiety and stress. The main means of maintaining inner peace are religious activities such as prayer, dhikr, and reading the Qur'an, as well as values such as patience, tawakal, and ikhlas. Sufi practices, including tafakur, muhasabah, and dhikr, can reduce blood pressure and improve sleep quality (Husna, 2024). Spiritual principles also play a role in reducing cortisol hormone levels in the body, which has a direct impact on improving a person's psychological condition (Walida, 2025). Furthermore, other studies have also proven that Al-Quran murottal therapy is successful in reducing anxiety in pregnant women, which shows a clear relationship between spirituality and emotional stability. (Nugraha, 2020).

To overcome stress and emotional disorders, a combination of spirituality with psychological techniques known as psychoreligious therapy is an option. very appropriate. According to Dadang Hawari, psychoreligious therapy is a therapy healing carried out with a religious approach in increasing resilience and stamina to solve various life problems that cause psychosocial tension (Dadang, 2018). Research proves that trauma recovery can be overcome with holistic therapy, which combines contemporary psychological procedures with Islamic principles that are more successful in improving mental healing standards (Syifa & Nurjannah, 2024). The idea that this integrative method offers a comprehensive understanding of the causes, effects, and management of stress from a body and soul perspective simultaneously is further supported by a 2019 study published in *Psychis Jurnal Psikologi Islam*. This shows how important it is to integrate spirituality and science within the framework of contemporary health psychology (Rena, 2019).

All things considered, this research suggests that a comprehensive and integrative strategy is needed for effective stress and emotion management. To achieve balance between body and mind, biological approaches involving understanding the nervous and hormonal systems, psychological approaches involving emotion regulation and social support, and spiritual approaches involving worship and religious principles all work together. To address today's mental health issues, it has been shown that integrating psychological, physiological and religious principles is not only feasible but also highly relevant and necessary for emotion processing.

CONCLUSION

Managing emotions and stress requires a holistic and integrative approach, combining physiological, psychological, and spiritual aspects. From the analysis of 16 reviewed literatures, it was found that stress and emotions not only have an impact on mental health, but also affect physical conditions such as blood pressure and the immune system. Emotional regulation, social support, and spiritual practices such as dhikr, patience, tawakal, and reading the Qur'an have proven effective in reducing stress levels and improving psychological well-being. This study explains that There needs to be a holistic approach between physiological, psychological and

spiritual aspects in dealing with stress and emotions, so as to provide a more comprehensive solution in efforts to maintain physical and mental health.

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